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DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET FACTORS TO ENSURE THE GROWTH OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ENTERPRISE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAG EXPRESS BRAND STORES)

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Abstract: This article examines issues related to the analysis of marketing activities of enterprises and the evaluation of sales efficiency. The chain of branded stores "SAG EXPRESS" operating in the territory of Uzbekistan was selected as the object of the study. The research employed marketing analysis, benchmarking, statistical and econometric methods, particularly the Fourier analysis model. During the study, sales volumes for 2023–2024, regional distribution, price segments, and seasonal factors were analyzed. The results made it possible to identify leading, middle, and low-performing segments in store operations. Additionally, price sensitivity of demand and seasonal fluctuations in sales volumes were determined, and recommendations were developed to improve marketing strategies. The results of the study contribute to optimizing marketing activities of retail chains and increasing sales efficiency.

Key words: marketing analysis, sales efficiency, Fourier analysis, seasonality, demand analysis, price segmentation, sales dynamics, retail trade, marketing strategy, sales volume, economic analysis, benchmarking, econometric model, SAG EXPRESS, marketing activity.

INTRODUCTION

In today's uncertain market environment, strengthening a company's marketing focus and preparing and making informed management decisions requires meaningful marketing analysis. It can be viewed as a means of improving the company's performance and solving many problems, including assessing the market, its own capabilities, competitors' behavior, and more. The primary goal of analytical work conducted at a company is to strengthen its market position and enhance its competitiveness. In scientific and applied literature, this topic is studied from the perspectives of economics, management, marketing, and strategic analysis.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Drawing on international experience, it is evident that the advancement of non-cash payments and the digitalization of the financial sector in Uzbekistan have gained significant traction in both scientific research and analytical reviews in recent years. The theoretical frameworks of these processes and their practical applications have been extensively examined by prominent economists, including M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, E. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, and A. Marshall

It's worth noting the scholars who have made significant contributions to the development of marketing theory, although research conducted in the field of marketing in our country over many years has been based on national characteristics. These include Zh. Zaynalov, E. Shavkiev, M. Mukhammedov, M. Sharifkhodzhaeva, Sh. Ergashkhodzhaeva, Sh. Musaeva, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass observation methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis of the result. Thus, the analysis of the marketing activities of an enterprise is a systematic process of assessing and interpreting information about the marketing environment, strategy and tools, aimed at increasing the efficiency of marketing activities and achieving the commercial goals of the organization.

The main stages of the analysis of marketing and sales activities can be described in the following table 1:

Table 1. Main stages of analysis marketing activities and sales

Method/Tool	Description	Application
Sales structure analysis	Research of sales structure by products, regions, distribution channels.	Assess the share of each product/channel in total sales.
Analysis of sales dynamics	Study of changes in sales volumes over different periods.	Assessing growth or decline trends. Forecasting based on historical data.
Price elasticity of demand analysis	Evaluation of the dependence of sales volume on price changes.	Determining the optimal pricing policy to maximize profits.
ABC analysis	Classification of products by sales volume (A - the most profitable products, B - average profit, C - low profit).	Identify priority products to improve inventory management and distribution strategies.
Portfolio analysis	Evaluation of different products or brands based on their market share and growth rate.	Selecting strategies for growth in segments with high share and growth rates.
Analysis of sales seasonality	Assessing the dependence of sales on seasons, holidays and economic cycles.	Inventory and promotion planning, improved demand forecasting.
SWOT analysis	Assessing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the sales process.	Development of a sales strategy and risk minimization.
Demand forecasting	Forecasting future sales volume based on historical data and trends.	Optimization of production and warehouse stocks.

As part of the assessment of the effectiveness of marketing activities, key methods and tools for sales analysis were considered, allowing us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the current product sales strategy.

The object of the analysis was the chain of branded stores "SAG EXPRESS", specializing in the retail sale of branded products of the company LLC "SAG".

The SAG EXPRESS chain of branded stores is a network of specialized retail stores selling carpets and rugs throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan. The project was founded in 2021 as a retail arm of SAG and currently has over 15 locations throughout Uzbekistan. The company operates under a single brand, offering customers a wide range of products and a range of related services, including free delivery, professional room measurements, fitting, and trimming. This positions SAG EXPRESS not only as a carpet and rug retailer but also as a full-service interior design provider.

The chain offers several store formats: XP—flagship stores featuring art installations and exclusive carpet collections; XL—stores with a wide product range; and XS—compact express stores in city centers. This multi-format model allows the company to flexibly adapt to different customer categories and store locations. In each region, the stores are designed in a unified corporate style and operate under a standardized pricing policy, ensuring transparent purchasing conditions and increasing customer loyalty.

The company's digital presence also plays a significant role in product promotion and customer engagement. SAG EXPRESS actively uses online platforms and social media to inform consumers about new arrivals, promotions, and collection highlights. The official website and Instagram pages of individual stores serve as channels for direct communication with customers and drive online sales growth.

Thus, SAG EXPRESS can be considered a shining example of a modern retail chain that combines traditional retail approaches with innovative forms of customer engagement. The chain's development is taking place amidst a growing interest in interior design, making its operations relevant for analysis in the context of market transformations and consumer behavior in the region.

Since the launch of the SAG EXPRESS project in 2021, the company has been actively expanding its geographic presence, opening new retail outlets throughout Uzbekistan. As Table 2 shows, the network covers a significant number of regions, including Samarkand, Navoi, Tashkent, Khorezm, Karakalpakstan,

Surkhandarya, and Jizzakh regions. The geographic distribution of retail outlets demonstrates the brand's strategic commitment to being closer to the end consumer in all key administrative-territorial units of the country.

Active expansion in recent years is also noteworthy—more than 10 stores were opened in 2023–2024 alone, indicating an intensive phase of business scaling. The variety of formats (XL, XS, and specialty stores in small towns) reflects the company's flexible approach to developing distribution channels based on the region's population density and consumer activity (table 2).

Table 2. General information about SAG EXPRESS branded stores

No.	Brand store	Location	Address
1	Samarkand Rudaki	Samarkand region	Samarkand, Rudaki Street, 55
2	Samarkand Jambay	Samarkand region	Jambay district, Katta Qishlok street, house No. 33
3	Samarkand Helion	Samarkand region	Ibn Sina Street, 23A
4	Samarkand Elevator	Samarkand region	Samarkand, Spitamenshoh St. 270, Elevator-building plant
5	Navoi Yangi bazaar	Navoi region	city, Navoiy, st., Galvbv Shokh
6	Navoi 2	Navoi region	Islam Karimov Street
7	SAG XL Marvarid	Navoi region	Navoi region, Karmaninsky district, Karmany street, 9th house
8	SAG Bekobod	Tashkent region	Bekabad city, 13-Microdistrict st. A. Temura
9	SAG xs	Tashkent city	Tashkent city, Small Ring Road, 22-24
10	SAG XL	Tashkent city	Tashkent city, Big Ring Road street, 111
11	Showroom "Urgench"	Khorezm region	Urgench city, Yogdu street
12	Brand store in Urgench	Khorezm region	Urgench city, st. I. Dustov 114
13	Khiva	Khorezm region	the city of Khiva
14	Shimbay store	Republic of Karakalpakstan	Chimbay district, «Berdakh» MFY Doslik mahalla 6th house
15	Brand store Nukus	Republic of Karakalpakstan	Nukus city, Ernazar Alakoz street, 171/ house No. 2
16	SAG Express Surkhandarya	Surkhandarya region	Termez city, opposite Grand Almaz
17	SAG Express Jizzakh	Jizzakh region	Jizzakh city, Kahraman mahalla

Given the geographic scale and diversity of store formats, analyzing their operational efficiency and assessing sales structure and dynamics is essential. At this stage, it's important to determine the extent to which the store chain is meeting its commercial objectives, ensuring stable sales turnover, optimal inventory turnover, and high customer engagement.

In reviewing the marketing and sales activities of SAG EXPRESS, it is worth considering the following aspects:

- Sales volumes by region and store: identifying the most and least efficient points of sale, as well as factors influencing differences in turnover.
- Format efficiency: a comparative analysis of XP, XL, and XS format stores in terms of revenue, operating profit, and margins.
- Seasonal and regional patterns of demand: assessing the impact of climatic, cultural and infrastructural factors on sales activity in various regions.

This approach will not only allow for a quantitative assessment of store performance but also identify key growth areas and opportunities for improving sales efficiency. The data sources for the marketing and sales analysis were data from SAG Express branded stores of SAG LLC for 2023-2024, taken from the 1C ERP system.

An analysis of SAG EXPRESS's revenue dynamics for the period 2023–2024 revealed steady growth, from a baseline of approximately 10 billion soums in January 2023 to 46.5 billion soums in December 2024. This indicates positive development in the company's sales activities. Secondly, a clear seasonality of sales is

evident: peak revenue levels are recorded in December of each year (29.5 million in 2023 and 46.5 million in 2024), which is most likely due to pre-holiday demand.

For a detailed revenue analysis, we analyzed revenue dynamics for SAG EXPRESS branded stores operating for more than two years. An analysis of revenue for seven stores for 2023–2024 allowed us to identify three stable segments based on profitability: leaders, mid-tier, and underperformers.

Leading group SamExpress1 and Magazin Urganch form the core of the retail chain, demonstrating consistently high revenue with a pronounced seasonality. These stores' average monthly sales are approximately 7,500–8,000 million soums, with peaks reaching 11,309 million soums (SamExpress1, December 2023) and 8,926 million soums (Urganch, December 2024). The main sales peaks occur in November–December and August.

Middle segment The mid-market segment is represented by Xiva, Jizzax, Bekobod, and Termiz stores, with average monthly revenue ranging from 1,200 to 2,200 million soums. These stores have shown moderate but steady growth. For example, Jizzax increased its revenue from 56 to 1,316 million soums, and Bekobod from 373 to 1,674 million soums. All mid-market stores experience a seasonal peak in December and growth in September–October, which may be related to preparations for the holidays and seasonal cold snaps.

Outsider Fergana remains the leading store in terms of revenue, with average revenue of approximately 700 million soums. Its growth over the past two years has averaged +240 million soums, with minimal seasonal fluctuations. This may indicate a weak market position or high competition in the location.

Seasonality is generally pronounced for most stores: December is the most profitable month for almost all, with peaks in August and September. This suggests the influence of seasonal demand (preparation for holidays, seasonal cold snaps, etc.) on revenue structure.

Thus, stores differ significantly in terms of revenue levels and dynamics, as well as their susceptibility to seasonal fluctuations (table 3).

Table 3. Classification of stores by revenue and seasonal activity

Group	Shops	Avg. revenue / month	Seasonality coefficient*	The nature of seasonality
Leaders	SamExpress1, Urganch	7,500–8,000	1.6–1.8	High
Middle segment	Xiva, Bekobod, Jizzax, Termiz	1,200–2,200	1.2–1.5	Average/moderate
Outsider	Fergana	~700	~1.1	Weak

To analyze the cyclicity and nature of the dynamics of sales revenue, the econometric model of Fourier analysis was used.

Fourier analysis (analysis using the Fourier transform) A seasonal wave is a mathematical tool used to decompose complex time series into a sum of sinusoidal components. In economics and finance, it is used to identify hidden periodic patterns and cycles in data. The following equation is sometimes used as an analytical form of a seasonal wave:

$$\bar{y}_t = a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m (a_k \cos kt + b_k \sin kt),$$

Where k –degree of accuracy of the harmonic of a trigonometric polynomial;
 t –time.

This equation is a Fourier series where time (t) is expressed in radial units or degrees (table 4);

Table 4. Levels (y_t) at different phases of the cycle (in radians and degrees)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Radial measure	0	$\frac{\pi}{6}$	$\frac{\pi}{3}$	$\frac{\pi}{2}$	$\frac{2\pi}{3}$	$\frac{5\pi}{6}$	π	$\frac{7\pi}{6}$	$\frac{4\pi}{3}$	$\frac{3\pi}{2}$	$\frac{5\pi}{3}$	$\frac{11\pi}{6}$
Degrees	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330
Levels (y_t)	(y_1)	(y_2)	(y_3)	(y_4)	(y_5)	(y_6)	(y_7)	(y_8)	(y_9)	(y_{10})	(y_{11})	(y_{12})

The parameters of the Fourier series equation are found using the least-squares method. Without presenting the derivation here, we present the formulas used to calculate the above-mentioned parameters of the Fourier series equation:

$$a_0 = \frac{\sum y}{n}; a_k = \frac{2 \sum y \cos kt}{n}; b_k = \frac{2 \sum y \sin kt}{n}$$

Below we will construct equations for 7 brand stores and analyze each of them (table 5,6):

Table 5. Results of seasonal components of retail store revenue based on trigonometric Fourier decomposition

	A0	cos(t)	sin(t)	cos(2t)	sin(2t)	cos(3t)	sin(3t)
Magazin Urganch	5,048.6	198.4	- 770.8	- 52.6	-281.3	-73.4	- 411.8
SamExpress1	6,799.2	- 608.1	- 564.5	-288.6	11.5	21.0	-206.4
Magazin Xiva	1,535.5	163.5	- 237.4	28.2	- 98.5	-17.8	-123.6
Magazin Termiz	1,048.9	- 33.7	-31.7	6.2	- 40.1	16.6	1.9
Fergana Store	766.1	- 64.1	-40.0	- 24.1	19.4	22.0	- 33.2
Jizzax Store	1 139.1	- 81.1	- 126.4	- 32.7	- 61.3	- 7.9	27.9
Magazin Bekobod	1,287.3	27.3	- 140.9	14.5	- 27.4	5.2	- 35.6

Table 6. Comparative analysis of the results of Fourier analysis

	A0	Amplitude of the first harmonic	Second harmonic amplitude	Amplitude third harmonics
Magazin Urganch	5,048.6	795.9	286.2	418.3
SamExpress1	6,799.2	829.8	288.8	207.5
Magazin Xiva	1,535.5	288.3	102.4	124.8
Magazin Termiz	1,048.9	46.3	40.6	16.7
Fergana Store	766.1	75.6	31.0	39.8
Jizzax Store	1 139.1	150.2	69.5	29.0
Magazin Bekobod	1,287.3	143.5	31.0	36.0

An analysis of seven stores reveals significant unevenness in revenue distribution and seasonal activity. The stores can be clearly divided into three groups based on average revenue (parameter A0 in the Fourier equation):

Leaders—SamExpress1(6799)andUrganch(5049). Together, they account for over 65% of the total revenue of the entire network. In addition to high revenue, they also demonstrate the highest seasonal volatility: the total amplitude of the Fourier components is 1971.4 for SamExpress1 and 1931.3 for Urganch. This indicates a strong dependence on the season, particularly annual and quarterly fluctuations (dominated by first- and third-harmonic sine waves). For these stores, peak sales can exceed baseline sales by 25-30%, which is critical for inventory management, staffing, and advertising. Meanwhile, slow months can reduce sales by almost 1,000-1,200 units below average.

Middle segment—Xiva(1535),Bekobod(1287) and Jizzax(1139). Revenue is 3-5 times lower than that of the leaders. Xiva also has a relatively high seasonality—757, indicating the presence of clearly defined peaks. Bekobod and Jizzax have a more modest range—372 and 294, respectively. This means seasonal planning is less critical here, but there is potential for increased activity in certain months. Demand can fluctuate by 15–20% of the average.

Outsiders—Termiz(1049)andFergana(766). They have the lowest level of seasonality:203 and 265. Sales are flat, with no significant peaks. This could be due to low traffic, limited demand, or an outdated format. With such stability but low revenue, it's advisable to consider either reopening or closing the store if fixed costs aren't covered by revenue.

Another important factor reflecting the effectiveness of marketing activities is the analysis of demand and the study of its components.Demand analysis— is the process of studying the volume and structure of consumer demand for goods and services to identify the factors influencing its formation, change, and dynamics, as well as to predict future consumer behavior in the market. For a detailed analysis of demand, we decided to construct a histogram of the price-sales volume relationship.¹for branded stores for 2024.

1 A price-volume histogram is a graph that displays changes in sales volume across price ranges, allowing you to identify price levels that generate the highest revenue.

An analysis of seven stores revealed (Diagrams 5 and 6) that demand is primarily concentrated in price ranges up to 200,000 soums, particularly in the 100,000-200,000 soums segment, where SamExpress1 and Urganch clearly lead. Bekobod stands out for its highest sales volume in the low-price segment (up to 100,000 soums), indicating a strong focus on the mass market. All stores experience a sharp decline in sales as they move into higher price categories, particularly those over 300,000 soums. This suggests that demand is primarily concentrated in affordable and mid-priced products. Xiva, Fergana, and Termiz stores demonstrate comparatively low volumes, which may be due to a limited customer base or product range. Overall, the market is clearly price-sensitive, and the sales strategy should focus on maintaining and expanding the product range in the 200,000 soums segment.

An analysis of the sales structure across seven stores reveals a pronounced focus on price categories up to 200,000 soums, which account for between 74% and 87% of total sales at each store. Magazin Urganch and SamExpress1 have the most balanced structure, with sales in the up to 100,000 soums segment accounting for 30% and 32%, while sales in the 100,000–200,000 soums category account for 47% and 46%, respectively; for a total of 77% and 78%.

Magazin Xiva and Magazin Termiz have a 52% and 55% share of sales in the mid-price segment (100,000–200,000 soums), the highest among all retail outlets, while the low-price segment accounts for 26% in both cases. Magazin Fergana and Magazin Jizzax have high sales shares in the up to 100,000 soums category—34% for both—and 48% and 51% in the 100,000–200,000 soums segment, indicating a strong focus on targeting budget-conscious customers (table 7).

Table 7. Distribution structure of carpet sales by price segments and stores.

	Magazin Urganch	SamExpress1	Magazin Xiva	Magazin Termiz	Fergana Store	Jizzax Store	Magazin Bekobod
up to 100	30%	32%	26%	26%	34%	34%	58%
100-200	47%	46%	52%	55%	48%	51%	29%
200-300	15%	15%	15%	13%	12%	9%	10%
more than 400	7%	7%	6%	7%	6%	5%	3%

Meanwhile, Magazin Bekobod stands out for its most skewed structure: 58% of sales are in the price range up to 100,000 soums, significantly above average, while the 100,000-200,000 soums category accounts for only 29%, and sales of goods over 400,000 soums account for only 3%, half that of most other stores. Across all locations, the 200,000-300,000 soums segment remains relatively underdeveloped, ranging from 9% (Jizzax) to 15% (Urganch, SamExpress1, Xiva). Sales in the over 400,000 soums category have the smallest share: an average of 5-7%, with the exception of Bekobod, where their share is minimal.

These data confirm that the main competitive struggle takes place in the range of up to 200 thousand sum, forming approximately 80% of the sales base for almost all participants.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

An important area of development for the processing industry is increasing the economic potential of enterprises. This increased potential not only allows for the population's growing demand for goods and services but also increases their exports, ensuring the international competitiveness of the country's economy. Theoretical and practical research conducted to examine this issue has led us to the following conclusions:

1. The concept of "economic potential" is a complex economic category encompassing all levels and sectors of the national economy. Therefore, in pursuit of this goal, we refined the definition of economic potential, which allowed us to introduce some limitations to the scope of our research. First, we used it to assess the potential of individual enterprises, and second, we applied a decomposition method to examine various aspects of economic potential analysis.

2. Scholars from various countries agree that economic potential includes many elements, including production, labor, marketing, innovation, and others. Although there are differences in the definitions of these elements, the general approach is a systems approach to analyzing economic potential. This determined the purpose, objectives, and scope of the study.

3. Studying economic potential is a complex analytical process involving the processing of large volumes of information. Given this, the primary goal of the study was to apply mathematical modeling and programming methods to improve the objectivity and informativeness of the analytical results.

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